

Strategic Directions of Management of Innovation Activities at Silk-Producing Enterprises

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Abstract: The article highlights strategic directions of innovation management of silkworm breeding enterprises in order to increase competitiveness. Positive factors influencing the innovation activity of enterprises are analyzed, and indicators determining the effectiveness of innovation management are determined. Strategic directions of innovation management that serve the development of the enterprise are identified.

Keywords: Innovation, innovative activity, strategic directions, innovation process, system management, influencing factor, management approach, competence, enterprise.

Introduction. Innovations are currently the basis of economic, scientific, technical and social progress, acting as the main form of development in modern society. Innovation is the final result of innovative activity. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovation Activity", it is understood as scientific, technological, organizational, financial and commercial activity aimed at implementing innovative projects, as well as creating an innovative infrastructure and ensuring its activities. Innovative activity in modern conditions is a prerequisite for maintaining and strengthening the position of an enterprise in the market. It is based on many ideas - from simple ones, the implementation of which does not require significant investments, to global ones, which are based on the results of fundamental research and development and which cannot be implemented without serious investment costs. The choice of the method and direction of innovative activity of enterprises, as well as innovative projects for implementation, depends on the characteristics of their economic activities, resource, technological and scientific-technical potential, stages of the life cycle of equipment and technology, marketing strategies of the enterprise, market requirements.

It is necessary to develop the silk industry, which has long existed in Uzbekistan, based on innovative activities. Because this industry is not only a source of income, but also provides employment and increases the export potential of the Republic. It is known that Uzbekistan is the third largest producer of raw silk in the world, accounting for about 2% of world production. Over the past seven years, thanks to the reforms, the silk industry of Uzbekistan has been developing dynamically. The authorities of Uzbekistan are persistently reviving the traditions of sericulture on a new industrial and organizational basis. 74 sericulture clusters and 11 enterprises for harvesting silk have been created. The area of mulberry plantations has increased from 40 thousand to 55 thousand hectares. As a result, the volume of cocoon production has increased by 2.5 times, and the export of silk products - by 3 times. In Uzbekistan, about 26 thousand tons of raw cocoons are produced annually in more than

150 districts, systematic work is underway to strengthen the forage base by expanding the area of mulberry plantations.

The Government of Uzbekistan pays priority attention to the development of the silk industry in Uzbekistan. In the republic in recent years, as in many other industries, it was possible to solve the main problems in the silk industry, which had been holding back its development for a long time. The main factor in its development was the transition to the cluster method, which includes the entire process of production of finished products, starting from the development of the feed base, the organization of the processes of feeding and harvesting silkworm cocoons and ending with their deep processing and sale for export.

Moreover, benefits and preferences were introduced aimed at easing the tax and customs burden of silk industry enterprises, reducing transportation costs, improving the terms of credit for the sector, as well as social incentives for silkworm workers and home workers engaged in growing live silkworm cocoons. In particular, the silk industry has the following benefits and preferences:

- silkworm breeders are exempt from income tax, their work for the season is counted as annual work experience;
- silkworm breeding enterprises are exempt from social tax (in terms of funds allocated for the payment of sericulturists), land tax, property tax, and income tax (in terms of funds received from exports).

The state also compensates the following expenses of enterprises in the industry:

- transportation of silk products by air and rail to countries such as the USA, Turkey and the European Union (up to 50% of expenses);
- implementation of a drip irrigation system on mulberry plantations (up to 8 million soums per 1 hectare);
- construction of a borehole for irrigation of mulberry plantations with an area of more than 35 hectares (up to 120 million soums);
- purchase of carpet and silk weaving looms for hand weaving (2.7 million soums for each purchased loom).

At the same time, despite the positive trends in the development of the industry, it is necessary to note the factors that can give impetus to the further development of this sector in the near and long term.

Firstly, it is necessary to increase the production of local silkworm silk to volumes that cover the needs of domestic silkworm breeding enterprises, with the expansion of the sales market in the long term.

Secondly, one of the most important tasks facing domestic enterprises is to bring the quality of raw silk to class 4A in the near future, and in the future to class 6A. In the world market, mainly raw silk of higher quality (4A and higher) is purchased. The difference in price between quality 3A (on average \$ 47 / kg) and 4A (52-55 dollars / kg) reaches 5-8 dollars / kg, and 6A costs about 60 dollars / kg. Improving the quality of raw silk will directly affect the increase in income of enterprises and silkworm breeders.

Thirdly, another factor that will give a powerful impetus to the development of the industry is attracting investments to organize the production of products with higher added value. Today, the industry processes only about 25% of raw silk, and of the final products, mainly only silk fabric and hand-woven carpets have been established. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the fact that without improving the quality of raw silk, it is impossible to produce goods that could be in demand in the main markets for finished silk products in Europe and the USA.

There are the following problems in the organization of innovation activities at silk industry enterprises: First of all, the heads of silk industry enterprises prefer to use foreign experience rather than create a new type of product. Sometimes these experiments prove ineffective due to various factors. Secondly, there is a lack of expert leaders capable of applying innovative management methods at silk industry enterprises. Thirdly, the lack of improvement of regulatory documents governing intellectual property relations and income distribution in the "intellectual property owner-institute-producer" system. Fourthly, the lack of development of a system for stimulating innovation activities in the silk industry.

Thus, it serves to strengthen the system of organizing innovative activities at silk industry enterprises, radically changes the current situation, and implements not only economic but also social functions. The prospects of an enterprise cannot exist without innovative activities, since they affect not only the financial and economic condition of the enterprise, but also its spiritual growth. The basis is the organization and improvement of innovative activities at silk industry enterprises, the development of a specific strategy for the development and export of high-quality silk products that meet the requirements of the international market, and the development of a long-term development plan.

Along with the factors influencing innovation processes and innovation activities, it is appropriate to consider the factors influencing the innovative development of the enterprise. With the help of SWOT analysis, the strengths and weaknesses of the innovative development of silkworm enterprises, existing opportunities and risks with a negative impact are determined.

Table-1. SWOT analysis of innovative development of silkworm enterprises

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of regulatory documents for the creation and development of silkworm breeding enterprises; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of cheap labor; • High possibility of exporting products manufactured by the enterprise; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sufficient raw material base; • Availability of opportunities for the implementation of innovative processes; • Personnel with many years of traditional experience; • High profitability of network enterprises; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formation of a network as a single technological chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low competitiveness of network products; • Lack of organization of integration of science and production; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Departure of qualified personnel to other industries; • Lack of investment; • Level of obsolescence of materials and equipment at enterprises; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of raw materials; • Level of complexity of work; • Insufficient innovative potential; • Lack of knowledge and experience in applying the cluster method at enterprises.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits provided by the state to network enterprises; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to enter foreign markets; • Opportunity to improve the qualifications of employees; • Establishing cooperation between silkworm breeding enterprises and research institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low motivation to work; • Changes in market prices; • Unstable economic and political situation in countries; • Competitive environment in the international market; • Due to natural factors, the supply of cocoon raw materials is decreasing.

Conclusion. The level of sustainability of innovative development of a developing enterprise has the greatest impact on its current economic situation. It is clear that an innovative sustainable enterprise must have a large amount of accumulated capital, fixed

assets and own funds that can be used to develop and implement innovative projects. As a result of the analysis of factors, it is clear that there are a number of problems that have a negative impact on the innovative development of enterprises in the silk industry:

- ✓ low quality of innovation management in silk industry enterprises;
- ✓ inability to develop an innovation development strategy that corresponds to the current economic situation of the enterprise;
- ✓ insufficient level of development of innovation infrastructure;
- ✓ lack of effective methods for introducing innovative technologies into the production process of the enterprise.

A necessary condition for achieving sustainable innovative development of the silk industry are considered to be strategic directions for managing innovative activities of enterprises in the silk industry, namely:

- developing a set of measures in accordance with the mission and strategy of enterprises to improve innovative processes occurring in the silk industry;
- ensuring the availability of resources for the implementation of innovative projects, integration of innovative and investment activities;
- developing new ways to improve old ones and manage innovative development with the most reasonable combination of operational and strategic innovations;
- implementing a system for effectively identifying consumer needs for innovations, implementing innovative activities of the network based on systematic collection, analysis and use of relevant data;
- using modern effective methods and tools in the practice of managing innovative development of silkworm enterprises;
- creating opportunities for special training and professional development for managers and employees of enterprises;
- developing a set of measures to identify threats that may arise at the stages of innovative processes and their neutralization.

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